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Deciphering the Diasporic Consciousness in Taslima Nasrin's *French Lover*

Abstract

The expatriate writers use their pen as non-violent potent weapon to create powerful literatures against injustices experienced by immigrants and to raise a voice of protest so as to educate people and the government about their rights and responsibilities. The major objective of any immigrant writer however, is to show, in what all ways an immigrant can come to terms with the new reality and new environment. Taslima Nasrin is a powerful woman in writings and her works were almost a thunderbolt struck on her readers as to make them aware of their surrounding atrocities and oppression.

This research paper entitled as Deciphering Diasporic Consciousness in Taslima Nasrin's *French Lover* is an earnest endeavor that focuses on Taslima Nasrin's life and her work *French Lover: A Novel (2001)*, in an attempt to place this Third-World Bangladeshi writer in the literary background of diasporic writing, particularly considering her life and double exile experiences and also tries to cast light on the inherent diasporic features of the work, *French Lover*. This paper also aims to discuss Taslima's portrayal of painful hardships and struggles endured by common Third-World immigrants in the land of freedom and equality – France.

Key Words: exile, diaspora, alienation, assimilation, loneliness, rootlessness, identity crisis, marginalization.

Introduction

Mainly, with the widening phenomenon of globalisation and even also before that, a large scale of migration and settlement outside native country resulted in the hybridisation of culture and thus a peculiar trend emerged in literature – a preoccupation with the experience of “diaspora”. Literature produced by diasporic writers simply give voice to the pinning experiences they encountered on the grounds of clash of two cultures, their attachment to mother country, racial discrimination and the subsequent alienation and rootlessness. Examining the possibilities and exploring the problems of experience of migrancy in the representative diasporic life and works of these writers, theoreticians like Homi K. Bhabha, Stuart Hall, etc. imparted a new momentum in the development and spreading of the theory of diaspora.

Taslima Nasrin, the queen of controversy used her words as a mightier sword to fight against the outdated, ill-conceived practices of her society and had to flee from her own motherland in 1994 when Muslim extremist groups put a price on her head due to the controversy flared up after the publication of *Lajja (Shame)* in 1993. In the midst of all the upheavals, she dauntlessly continues to publish her works. Though she took Kolkata as her adopted city that cradles a common culture, language and history with Bangladesh, there too she faced expulsion. This experience of Taslima being double exiled from Bangladesh as well as Kolkata instilled a diasporic consciousness in Taslima Nasrin and it is the foundation of this study. Implications and traces of themes like racism, homelessness, forced migration, oppression, cultural conflicts, identity crisis and struggling refugees are abundant in many of her works.

Taslima Nasrin has skillfully portrayed in the novel, *French Lover: A Novel* (2001) translated from Bengali by Sreejata Guha, the diasporic consciousness of an immigrant, Nilanjana, who came to France in search of much greener pastures and in the process

physically and culturally alienates herself from her native place. Her disillusionment ends when she realizes her lack of belonging to the foreign land. Her cultural affinity with Kolkata makes her an alien in France where she makes repeated attempts to transmute and transform her identity, struggling to shake off the ill effects of discriminations and demarcations by making adjustments and compromises.

Discussion

Expatriation or exile is often the result of some internal or external dilemma that demands displacement from one's own motherland. The term 'diaspora' has its etymological origin in a Greek word 'disapeir' –meaning dispersal, distribution, scattering or spreading. Though, this term has been widely used to denote the scattering of Jews, it is now used to denote any "number of ethnic and radical groups living distant from their traditional homelands" (Mandal 37). Displacement can be either forced or voluntary. In any of these cases, the immigrant will desire for his roots, a home, and a sense of belonging. Nirmal Selvamony in his essay "Migrancy in Literature" draws four important aspects of human migration, "abandonment of home, taking another's place, ontological change, and facelessness" (119). All these aspects can be traced in Nila's migration as well.

Most of the immigrants in the novel like Nila, Kishanlal, Sunil, Sanal, Mojammel, Bacchu, Modibo, Jewel and Rubel opted for Paris over their own country for securing a prosperous life. Nila says to the officer that she came to France in order "to live my life" (Nasrin 6). Nila married Kishanlal only because "Calcutta had been tormenting her and if she hadn't left that city, she would have surely died" (Nasrin 8) in the painful memory of her broken love affair with Sushanta. But Nila later understands the fact that "Life isn't easy in this foreign country" (Nasrin 79).

Taslina Nasrin describes the immigrants, Kishanlal, Sunil and Chaitali as "half-dead souls" (Nasrin 9). Taslima uses this metaphor to underline the pathetic plight of an immigrant

who lives his life just as automatons - 'half-dead' because of their torn identity – culturally and geographically. Nila's husband is now a French citizen, has literally waited for almost twelve years to establish himself in this nation. This long duration almost made him hard at heart, money-minded and selfish.

The immigrants like, Mojammel, Bachhu, Jewel and all are employers in Kishan's restaurant. Each of them had their own sad and toilsome life story and nostalgia to tell their beloved sister, Nila – their sole companion in the foreign country. Mojammel is a post graduate from Dhaka University and he is in a cut-throat passport – “This is when they remove the neck upwards from someone else's passport and stick your own photo in it” (Nasrin 32). Such a passport was bought by his father selling their land and is now doing 'illegal labour' because all the papers of immigrants have to be passed through and approved. Bacchu is another immigrant who is a doctor in India but in France he is cooking in Kishan's restaurant as his degree is not valid in France. Later, in the novel, when he failed to get papers in France, he started to Italy but, in his struggle to get there, he was hit by a train from back and dies. The immigrant brothers, Jewel and Rubel they too suffered a lot, “he had sold their land, collected lakhs of rupees and left Dhaka with dreams of a golden future and he came back there, physically, economically and mentally crippled” (Nasrin 276). Modibo was another immigrant, though not an Indian, who suffered all the pangs of expatriation even more badly than Indians because of his skin colour and African nationality.

Immigrants live a life of hell by sharing everything you have with others of six or more like them, in a small room, constantly under the dread of being thrown out of the country for ever. This is heart wrenching experience, for immigrants who came to alien lands to eradicate poverty and to live a better life; in turn they will have to live in utter poverty even worse than what they faced in their own land. Through these feebly portrayed Indian immigrants, Taslima is addressing the harsh realities and hardships; an immigrant faces in an

alien country where they have no belonging but just hostile environment, culture, rules, people, and government.

The very first formidable hurdle an expatriate have to face, is his/her need to define him/her as the new environment demands of them. Nila, even before defining herself to the new world, got her first identity not out of her name but out of her 'strange' appearance in this host land. Taslima Nasrin deliberately gives Nila the identity "Red Sari" (Nasrin 1) instead of a name, thus portraying her as someone devoid of any face, existence or even any significance or dignity. Her identity had been reduced to a mere object or a symbol that stands for her nationality, naivety, technological backwardness and lack of modernity against the modern, technologically developed, civilized, busy group of people. This casts light on the identity crisis an immigrant undergoes in his/her new world of alien culture. The experience of expatriation not only gradually disconnects the individual from his roots; simultaneously it cleaves his identity as well as the meaning of his entire existence, and will feel themselves as strange creatures rather than a human being. Thus, the quest for identity or self forms the core of the diasporic consciousness of an immigrant.

The moment one becomes an expatriate, he/she will try to adjust him/herself with the new environment mainly in two extreme ways – cultural assimilation and cultural alienation – as an attempt of self definition. In this attempt, he may either assimilate his identity with his host country at the cost of his ties with the native country, or he may resume his ties with the homeland and see the people around as 'the other'. Nila was striving to break off from the roots but at the same time she feels the pangs of being uprooted and alienated along with the sense of lack of belonging. This is evident in her words "It's a whole new world, totally strange" (Nasrin 28). She, in her extreme identity crisis even wonders "if she was visible" (Nasrin 65) to her 'other' world.

Relationships have a major impact on one's identity. Through the relationship with Benoir, Kishanlal, Danielle and Sunil, Nila acquires different identities that moulded in her a new personality. Taslima Nasrin, beautifully attributed adjectives to the protagonist's name in accordance with the role she plays in that relationship. Thus, in her relationship with Kishan, her name "Nila" attributes the qualities of "the bride, the doll, the visitor" (Nasrin 17) hence show the lack of attachment and the want of belonging in the relationship between Kishan and Nila. Likewise, all her western acquaints – Benoir, Catherine, Danielle and her friends – gave her a new identity, "Nila, the hunted, friendless, helpless animal", (Nasrin 205) this was her final identity in France. We can notice very often that, Nila is very much conscious of her diasporic existence and suffers from every drop of dislocation, dispossession, alienation, hybridity and above all dissatisfaction on 'not belonging to' the new country.

Kirpal says, "there is a compelling need in the expatriate – perhaps as a mechanism of defence against total facelessness – to cling to his own traditions and to mix with people of his own country" (48). This is what Nila tries to do, she tries to locate an atmosphere of familiarity in the unfamiliar, vast city of Paris. She comes to Kishanlal's hotel with a feeling that at least around her everything will seem very familiar and homely. She talks with the people of her ethnicity that too in her own mother tongue, Bengla. Nila felt the magic of companionship, "the effect of finding so many Bengalis. Her voice gained strength. Nila presumed even her soul was strengthened" (Nasrin 31). She believed that a familiar atmosphere may give her the sense of security and the assurance of not losing her identity and her inborn belongingness to a particular community. For the Indian immigrant workers of Kishan's restaurant, Nila's arrival was a near comfort – "The boys found a long-lost sister in Nila" (Nasrin 31). In the case of Kishanlal, he was a loner and was leading a life of seclusion from the outside world of Paris. Kishan usually wades off his loneliness by arranging get-togethers in his home – a union of people of same culture, nationality and history.

After her mother's death and thereby losing her last tie and even her identity associated with Calcutta, Nila got immersed in melancholy. She was "searching in the dark for darkness" (Nasrin 163) – a state of disillusionment and identity crisis. The realisation that "she was unwanted in this city" (Nasrin 174), thwarted her dignity. In search of four walls she approached all her so called companions but all shut the door against her. She realised that "no one was expecting her...Everyone thought the girl from Calcutta would stay there. Even Chaitali had done the simple math and realized that Paris wasn't for Nila and she wasn't for Paris. She stepped around . . . unwelcome and uninvited" (Nasrin 175). The loneliness and this segregation was so overwhelming that it engulfed her fully enough to feel the existential crisis and she asked herself "Who am I? I am nothing, nobody. I have no friends, no relatives. My life is a crumpled mess" (Nasrin 223).

"The expatriate as he moves from one culture to another may need to locate himself/herself afresh in relation to the centre" (Jain 16). In this process they employ a lot of strategies like learning language, creating a new identity distinct from their real identity, cutting off from their roots, trying to mingle in social life in new environment, learning the codes and mores of the society, creating western companions, owning a house and so on. Nila too tried to acculturate into her dream world, Paris.

As her first strategy of assimilation, she changed her typical Indian outlook, did menial jobs and tried to learn French through books and by interacting with people. She realised that French is a difficult language to learn and "this was one language that you couldn't learn from books" (Nasrin 92). Then, she made herself acquainted with Danielle and Catherine but, that relationship soon end up in a great amiss.

Once assimilation process is complete then the world you longed for before will cease to exist. This same idea is conveyed by Kishan in the novel as he speaks to Nila, "Let a few years pass and you'll see yourself finding India a strange place. That's life, Nila: a habit and

nothing else. Once you get used to the life here, you won't be able to adjust in India although that's where you were born and raised" (Nasrin 28). This indeed happened. She felt strange back in Calcutta and out of her loneliness and frustration she came back to Paris. After her return she wanted to rent a house, it was almost her last strategy of assimilation – "In migrating from one country to another, migrants inevitably become involved in the process of setting up home in a new land" (McLeod 211). This dream of her almost shattered to dust, because of tenant policy which says, an immigrant will need a guarantor for renting a home. In all these situations, Nila, the "migrant tries to appropriate materials not his own, and when appropriated, leaves them undigested" (Selvamony 122).

Nila's first day in France was an ordeal for her, after encountering racial antagonism and marginalisation for the first time in the airport. She herself thought of the situation – "If the red nuisance wasn't standing there, it would have cleared the fence long ago. The girl too felt she was a nuisance" (Nasrin 2). Even though, she had a sort of distaste for Calcutta and its patriarchal system of oppression, she never experienced such a racial persecution in her homeland that bruises one's individuality and identity. "She felt the corner was like a cage in the zoo. Everyone looked at her through the invisible cage as they walked past – they saw a strange animal with black eyes, dark hair and dark skin. The girl kept her eyes, the guilty ones, on the ground" (Nasrin 3). The biggest irony was that initially, Nila too was a racist, and believed herself to be "almost - whites" (Nasrin 10), a colonial mentality that Britain had left for Indians to segregate among themselves and others. Racist antagonism strikes her again in a bus when she took a few minutes more to search her ticket out from her bag. She was the only non-white in the bus and the officer suspected her because she had a 'brown' skin which in strange contrast with other passengers. She feels victorious as she proved him wrong.

Benoir was a handsome French man, who was preoccupied with the thought of Third-World women as sensuous beauties and was “keen to uncover the mystery of this mysterious woman” (Nasrin 164). But, her relationship with Benoir also failed, mainly because it was difficult for her to give up her ‘strange’ – as he believed – “habits, her language, her culture, her nature” (Nasrin 79) just because she loved him. In another instance, while talking with Benoir, Nila felt that she will remain in France forever “an Indian, poor, starving, pauper, an immigrant here to destroy French culture” (Nasrin 234). These were the words of an immigrant who was frustrated and thwarted by the marginalisation and segregation experienced in France.

In whatever way Nila may try to evade her connection with India, as an attempt to escape from her painful past experiences or as the process of adaptation into the new country of freedom, she will remain an Indian within. When the French officials examined her bag and later Indian currency, she was brimming with patriotism initially and talked to them in stern voice. In Kishan’s home too Nila searched for Rabindranath music as a solace but instead she got music of French singer, Edif Paif and for Nila “An unknown chirping in an unknown land can make one feel even more alone” (Nasrin 26).

Immigrants like Kishanlal, Sunil and Chaitali opted for a migrant status in Paris. However, they could not break away clean from their own culture. Kishan wanted a wife from India. He wanted her to dress like an Indian bride always, cook Indian food and to show all the duties towards him like any other Indian women. Kishan even gives his restaurant, names of Indian monuments – ‘Tajmahal’ and ‘Lal Killa’, which was later, changed to ‘Gandhi’.

Sunil and Chaitali, as a family decided to stay back retaining all their cultural and national ties. Nila felt at home, when she is in their house because Sunil had all the collections of Indian songs, especially Rabindranath Sangeet, Bengali books, pictures of three

famous Bengalis – Tagore, Boss and Vivekananda as well as pictures of all Indian gods and goddesses in his home. Sunil and Chatali even celebrate the great Indian festival Durga Puja in Paris along with a group of other immigrant Indians in France. They just harboured Indian festivals, tradition, customs and culture along with them to their new abode.

Food is a cultural identity. Nila cooks food for her western friends, the Indian typical cuisine of variety of fried and spicy food. Kishan too prefers Indian food in France and thus he got the idea of serving Indian food disguised in French flavours in his restaurants. So, sensitivity to food, rules and customs is significant in bridging cross-cultural differences and in building relationships. Immigrants retain their roots with their culture, tradition and nation, mainly through their food habits.

Nila's initial fascination and obsession towards the Whites, began to shatter and subside with subsequent cultural shocks and finally resulted in a feeling of uprootedness. However, she decided not to return to India thus, the concept of 'home' becomes nostalgia. Though, it is an unpleasant reminiscence of the past, she always yearns for a home or a homeland which in her own terms “spells shelter, security, peace and joy” (Nasrin 291) and much to her knowledge, it is ideal but never real or a land ‘never returned’, an ‘imaginary homeland’. Swaraj Raj claims in his essay that all discourses of theory of diaspora: define diasporas as the deterritorialized other of the territorial nation-state . . . Besides this, in such discourses the desire for the Real, the realm of the impossible – *there is no place like home* – the mother, the originary home, the homeland haunts the diasporic consciousness, and this desire for the home is taken as the defining feature of diaspora. The entire emphasis of interpretive endeavour rests on hermeneutics of nostalgia. (55)

Nila felt herself a strange person or an alien creature devoid of any space for herself as “in this city everyone had somewhere to go to, except she. No one waited for her, anywhere” (Nasrin 26). Here, Taslima by projecting Nila's in-depth feeling of lack of

belongingness and homelessness, gives voice to her diasporic sensibility of intense longing for a home, the trauma of lack of belonging either in her homeland, Bangladesh or in the adopted homeland, Kolkatta. Kirpal says, “Home, for the characters is not a quest for spatial identity but a search for roots. It is also a hunt for self in a world arbitrarily divided into the white world – progressive, developed – and the coloured world – backward, underdeveloped” (71).

Her mother was the only connection that tied her to her motherland as an invisible umbilical cord. She often perch on the branches of nostalgia about her mother. When she came to know that her mother is ill, she felt the guilt of abandoning her mother as well as her mother country, when both needed her for the most. She felt like “the tree of her dreams lay uprooted, the thousand lamps were blown out . . . Nila was flown on this destructive wind into a shining household” (Nasrin 13). Taslima Nasrin uses the imagery of uprooted tree and destructive wind to intensify the state of delirium in which Nila is trapped. As an immigrant she is uprooted from her homeland and is dispersed by the destructive wind or the hardships of life to a totally strange and alien land where there is only loneliness and rootlessness. She feels intense identity crisis in the foreign land and feels as if “she was nobody, a strange piece of flesh whom they’d all like to avoid” (Nasrin 119).

Taslima Nasrin places Nila’s mother, Molina’s self-less image as analogous to mother country, India. Nila is attached to both her mother and country in the same way. She knows that they both are “beyond her love and tenderness, her respect and adulation. Nila had kept it all back until it was too late. She desperately wanted to turn the clock back, to correct her mistakes. But time swept on as usual, carrying with it all mistakes, all wrongs” (Nasrin 142). Molina and the motherland both demanded from her only one thing “Stay in the country. Don’t go abroad” (Nasrin 145). But, she feels that India too is not her abode “this house isn’t mine and I am not of this house” (Nasrin 156).

When Nila's mother died, everything around her seemed dark and hopeless. She wanted to escape from Calcutta because:

For Nila, Calcutta was now a burning ghat. It used to be her mother's cotton sari where she wiped her sweat and tears . . . it used to be Molina's large, black eyes . . . and wherever Nila dived, they searched for Nila. It was as if someone had wrapped up . . . into a parcel of darkness and hurled it far, dug a hole . . . and dropped Calcutta into its depths and run away. Now there was no one called Calcutta, nothing called Calcutta. (Nasrin 157)

Nila realised her double diasporic status because, "For Nila, the sorrow wasn't for a month but for three days. She was married and had gone into another family. Now she didn't have so many duties towards her mother" (Nasrin 150). This reality shattered her within and she stood alone "between life and death, asking questions" (Nasrin 150). Taslima voices Nila's question to the whole world that "do women ever have a land of their own or a motherland?" (Nasrin 292). This is the 'other' aspect of immigrant life which Taslima stresses on – the status of women expatriates who are always double diasporic and double marginalised in a new land due to their gender as well as by the institution of marriage and patriarchal system.

In her return journey to Paris, she felt a desire for home which is not present either in India or in France, a kind of utter homelessness – "the puffy white clouds were flying somewhere, home perhaps. Everyone went home, except Nila" (Nasrin 163). Here Nila experiences a homing desire, which is "not the same as the desire for a 'homeland'. The *homing desire* is the desire to create the home *where one is*, that is in the host culture, through tangential affiliations" (Raj 56). Now, Nila expects nothing from the city, Paris except a shelter, she needed just "four walls and a roof over her head" (Nasrin 174). This is because, "A home is where one locates oneself after leaving behind the public space or all space that is not home" (Selvamony 116). Thus, the desire for a home forced her to rent a house.

While in France, Nila felt herself lonely, alienated and marginalised in this new land and her life was totally in a chaos. She herself felt this spick and span perfection as smothering and suffocating and very soon she went to India because of her mother's illness. There too the situation was worse because she felt that Calcutta has changed a lot to an extent that she perceived herself detached from her own country. She felt "it looked a little dingier, there was more filth on the footpaths, the air was a little more polluted, there was more traffic on the roads . . . The houses looked more worn out . . . the shops smaller . . . and the people darker" (Nasrin 131). The reason for her awkwardness is revealed by her driver Ramkiran that "Didi, *you* have changed. Calcutta is exactly the way you left it" (Nasrin 131). Kirpal says that "returning to the mother country after several years only accentuates the feeling of rootlessness in the expatriate as he realises how different and distant he has become from his native people and traditions" (49).

While in France, she was writhing in isolation and search for a companion, on whose shoulder, she can rest her head but in Calcutta she yearned for the "rare solitude" (Nasrin 136) and feels uprooted. After her mother's death she was aimless and vulnerable like a crying child who lost its protective and caring abode of mother's womb; she is now alone without an umbilical cord. "Now she didn't feel Calcutta was her own. She began to feel as if she had never known it . . . For Nila, Calcutta was now a burning ghat" (Nasrin 157). Neither she can now remain in Calcutta nor did she want to go back to the alien land. She felt herself rootless and "Nila surrendered herself to the uncertain" for-ever. Even her relationship with Benoir too was not enduring because she knew that one day "he would merge into the faceless crowd and Nila would stand there, neither here nor there" (Nasrin 168). She now feels that she does not have a proper place to live in and she is nothing but an outsider or an intruder for others. So, a migrant is ultimately "homeless despite having lived in two cultures. He has become the Marginal Man" (Kirpal 49). Kirpal says that "expatriates stay on as

marginal, “nowhere men”, unable to find solace in the new country, unable to discard the old” (89).

This very existential crisis paves her way to the decision to move ahead in the same unfamiliar alien land as she knows, she has no other place to go. This realisation is another feature of diaspora theory – a ‘home of no return’. Nirmal Selvamony in his essay “Migrancy in Literature” stresses on this idea and says:

In biology migration is not simply a movement from one place to another, but returning to the original location. But in the postcolonial context migration does not involve return to home-location. A movement away from one’s home-location, and taking permanent residence in the target-location characterize any human migration”. (118)

In almost all diasporic Third-World writings, there is an overall impression of perpetual movement and aimlessness as the journey motif predominates. Restlessness places the role of a catalyst in all these journeys, whether it’s between countries, cities or just a sail, ride in car, train, buses or simply a walk. From the beginning till the end, Nila is traveling aimlessly from one place to another in the hope of securing a happy life full of love and security. Nila was restless; the invisible omniscient narrator of the novel reveals the protagonist’s inner mind by saying that “Nila knew she had the rest of her life to look around. But she felt a dance of impatience in all her nerves” and further adds that, she was “Waiting to be free, although she didn’t know free of what or free to go where” (Nasrin 25). The writer here points, Nila’s aimlessness and restlessness and pangs of inability of settlement.

In her restlessness she walked incessantly whether in room or in street, she “walked from one room to another, her footsteps her only companion” (Nasrin 27). She just wanted “to go somewhere far off” (Nasrin 65) away from this lonely strange city. Throughout all her journey, she was half excited and half depressed. In her delirium, she boarded trains and buses “without knowing where it went” (Nasrin 66). Even also, when she came to know that

her mother is ill, she “walked alone in the misty streets” (Nasrin 112) not deciding exactly what to do.

Her travels were all futile and aimless. Nila never achieves the security and love she deserves but still at the end, she decides to settle down in Paris – bewildered, aimless and hopeless. Kirpal says, “This indeed is the expatriate’s dilemma. He is unable to return to the old idea of home despite its certainties and he is unable to find a new one in the adopted land. His is search without end, entailing countless journeys” (73).

Diasporic community, often caught in a kind of tug of war between two worlds, will try to keep hold of values of the homeland in the new atmosphere of the adopted land. In this attempt they often fall into the suffocating grasp of mental conflict, dilemma, and unanswered questions, which ultimately leads to identity crisis. The metaphor of ‘Trishanku’ has been commonly used to define such people who live in a state of in-betweenness or in a ‘neither here nor there’ status. Initially, she struggles to cope with her sense of ‘elsewhereness’ by creating a home for her by cherishing her neglected culture, customs in an effort to ward off exile and to prevent its devastation. But, after going through all the emotional traumas of emigration in her life, Nila realised that certain journeys never end and must go on in any case, even without hope, even without any ultimate goal of its own. She realised that ‘home’ is an imaginary concept, there is no place called home but it is a place of ‘no return’.

Conclusion

The blurb at the back of the novel, *French Lover* says, “Bold in concept and powerful in execution, *French Lover* is a fascinating glimpse into the workings of a woman’s mind as she struggles to come to terms with her identity in a hostile world”. Taslima Nasrin, a political migrant has been clearly presented in this novel the subject of losing one’s native

community and the struggle to cope with that loss in an alien environment. Nila, the protagonist's working of mind in the alien country is the main plot of this novel. In whatever way they may try to assimilate, immigrants will feel a powerful pull, partly because of their reluctance to give up the cultural baggage they have brought to the new land and partly because of the hostility or inhospitality they encounter there.

Nila as an immigrant, all her assimilation strategies were in vain as she was affected by her overwhelming experiences of European racism, Indian male chauvinism, lesbian and French lovers, and various other aspects of Bengali expatriate society. Thus, Nasrin gives a glimpse that Nila has to struggle in this foreign land for her identity because of being twice marginalised—first, she is a brown-skinned woman and second, she comes from a poor country like India. Thus, She never belonged to the new land and always were a ‘no where woman’ or in a state of ‘neither here nor there’, without reaching anywhere literally and just wandering aimlessly. Taslima Nasrin through her protagonist clearly draws the diasporic consciousness.

Like Taslima, Nila's expatriation is also double-edged. She is an expatriate in the patriarchal system of her own homeland and in a foreign world like France. Taslima Nasrin, an Indian Subcontinent exiled writer have shared the trauma of displacement and diasporic experience of lack of belonging in adopted land. The exiled writer, Nasrin misses her homeland, Bangladesh while in her foreign abode and her longing for Bengali culture, its art, music, tradition and festivities find place in her novel through Nila. Thus, Taslima Nasrin is affirming through her writings that diaspora is not merely scattering or dispersion but is a matrix of consciousness that encompasses various conflicting characteristics. With her experience of being an immigrant in various countries, she skillfully captures the experiences of the Third-World or more specifically of Indian immigrants with all its vibrant colours.

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